

Impact of Local and Landscape Factors on Spotted Wing Drosophila Epidemiology

Summary report of work conducted in 2022-2023.

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Summary

- Monitoring of Spotted Wing Drosophila (SWD) abundance at the James Hutton Institute over a ten year period (2013-2022) has shown that insect numbers were low until 2021, when numbers started to increase, and this increase was sustained in 2022. The numbers caught per trap per week are 10-100 fold lower than those reported for other areas of the UK. Monitoring will continue in 2023.
- Tests of varietal differences in SWD emergence from field-collected berries highlighted variability between genotypes of blackberry and raspberry. This variation did not correlate with berry sugar or acid content nor with skin elasticity.
- Further work is planned to test a selection of raspberry and blackberry varieties for their susceptibility to SWD in no-choice laboratory assays.

Citation: Karley AJ, Mitchell C, Smith A, Malloch G. 2023. Impact of Local and Landscape Factors on Spotted Wing Drosophila Epidemiology: Summary report of work conducted in 2022-2023.

Spotted Wing Drosophila monitoring in Scotland

The Spotted Wing Drosophila (SWD), *Drosophila suzukii*, is an invasive fruit fly which originated in Japan and has since spread across the world, first being detected in the UK in 2012. In the UK, SWD is a pest of soft and stone fruit, laying eggs in ripening and ripe fruit of many plant species. If left uncontrolled, SWD infestation can result in extensive financial losses for the grower.

SWD monitoring at the James Hutton Institute

SWD has been monitored in Scotland for ten years (2013-2022) at the James Hutton Institute in Dundee, following an established protocol (AHDB, 2022). Modified Droso traps with Cha-Landolt bait were positioned in and around fruit crops and checked for SWD every 1-2 weeks in the summer and every 2-4 weeks in the winter months. Ten traps were used during 2013-2021, and five traps in 2022. The number of female and male SWD adults was recorded in each sample and expressed as an average number per trap per week by averaging the trap catch over the preceding sampling period (i.e. between 1 and 4 weeks). No data are shown for 2013 as no SWD were detected in the traps.

In all years, the number of SWD caught at JHI (**Fig. 1**) remained very low until week 29 when an increase in numbers was observed. During years 2014-2020, the numbers remained low (<5 individuals per trap per week) for the rest of the year. In 2021 and 2022, there was a sharp uptick in the number of SWD caught from week 33 onwards and numbers remained high until week 47. This is demonstrated in the largest recorded peak weekly value of SWD per trap caught at JHI (**Fig. 2**), which was low throughout 2014-2020, but has shown an increase in the last two years.

Fig 1. The mean number of SWD per trap per week detected at JHI. Values for 2014 – 2021 are means of 10 traps, while values for 2022 are the mean of 5 traps.

Fig 2. The peak value of the mean number of SWD per trap per week caught at JHI in the period 2014 – 2022.

Fruit varietal differences in SWD susceptibility: a preliminary study

A small study was conducted to test crop varietal differences in SWD susceptibility. Replicate samples of multiple varieties of blackberries and raspberries were collected from field plots at the institute and the emergence of SWD individuals was scored. Subsamples of fruit were characterised for physical and chemical traits hypothesised to affect SWD oviposition (Lee et al., 2011; Burrack et al., 2013; Kinjo et al., 2013).

Berry samples from four blackberry varieties and 12 raspberry varieties were collected for emergence testing. Approximately 100 g of berries were placed in a ventilated tub at room temperature (~20 °C) and checked daily for three weeks. Any emerging SWD adults were counted and sexed.

The elasticity of twenty ripe berries of four blackberry and six raspberry varieties was measured using a Durofel meter which presses down on the berry until it splits. Each variety was given a score ranging from 0 to 100 with a higher score meaning that the skin was more elastic and required more force to burst. These berries were tested for sugar (Brix) and acid contents (pH).

The number of SWD adults emerging from blackberries and raspberries varied widely between the tested varieties (**Fig. 3**), with two varieties (Bramble 19-7 and 1657D-4) showing high values, and the remaining varieties showing moderate or low values. The sex ratio of emerging SWD was 50% female:50% male and did not vary between varieties (data not shown). There was variation in the elasticity of the skin in the blackberry varieties, but little variation between the raspberry varieties (**Fig. 4**), and there was no correlation between skin elasticity and emergence.

There was little variation in the acid and sugar content of the berries and these traits did not correlate with SWD emergence data (not shown).

Fig. 3. The number of SWD adults emerging from 100 g fruit samples of four blackberry (purple bars) and 12 raspberry varieties.

Fig. 4. The Durofel scores of four blackberry (purple bars) and six raspberry varieties. Values are the mean (\pm std dev) of $n=3$ samples.

Acknowledgements

We thank Nikki Jennings at James Hutton Limited for allowing us to sample berry variety trials. The Agriculture and Horticulture Development Board and Scottish Government funded the SWD monitoring in Scotland from April 2014 to March 2022. SWD monitoring and variety susceptibility testing in 2022 was supported by the Scottish Government's Strategic Research Programme (2022-2027) funded by the Rural & Environment Science & Analytical Services Division.

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